

VALIDATION OF ANALYSIS METHOD FOR DAPOXETINE HYDROCHLORIDE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18151914>

How to cite this Article: Khalid Mamoun A.*, Mai Mekki (2026). Validation Of Analysis Method For Dapoxetine Hydrochloride. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 136–140.

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Article Received on 05/12/2025

Article Revised on 25/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT Dapoxetine

Figure 1.1.

Dapoxetine

Dapoxetine Figure 1.1 a marketed as Priligy, among others, is a medication used for the treatment of premature ejaculation (PE) in men 18–64 years old. Dapoxetine works by inhibiting the serotonin transporter, increasing serotonin's action at the postsynaptic cleft, and as a consequence promoting ejaculatory delay. [*J Pharmaceut Biomed Anal*, **52**, 19-29] As a member of the selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) family, dapoxetine was initially created as an antidepressant. However, unlike other SSRIs, dapoxetine is absorbed and eliminated rapidly in the body. Its fastacting property makes it suitable for the treatment of PE, but not as an antidepressant.

KEYWORDS: Validation, Hplc, Quantitative, Accuracy.

INTRODUCTION

Validation of analytical procedure

The principle of validation of quantitative analytical procedures is widely spread today in all domains of activities where measures are made. The objective of validation of an analytical method is to demonstrate that the method is suitable for the intended use, such as evaluation of a known product for potency, and impurities. The intent of method validation is to provide scientific evidence that the analytical method is reliable and consistent before it can be used in routine analysis of product. The analytical method validation is governed by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH). (ICH1995), (Holcombe, 1998).

The key criteria for evaluation of an analytical method are: specificity, accuracy, precision, detection limit, quantitation limit, sensitivity, working range and linearity, robustness and recovery (Bansal, et al., 1998) and (Bansal, et al., 2004).

The type of method and analytical technique used will determine the nature and extent of the validation studies required. The most common methods for validation are identification, assay and impurities determination (Rockville, 2000) and (Rockville, 1987). Results for each applicable validation characteristic are compared against the selected acceptance criteria.

Besides ICH, other guidance can be referred for detailed information on the international requirements such as the US Food and Drug Administration guidance (FDA U.S. DHHS, 1996) and (Rockville2003). And the United States Pharmacopoeia (USP).

Validation of an analytical procedure is performed in order to demonstrate that the procedure is suitable for its intended use. Validation is performed in order to show that the result(s) generated by a particular analytical procedure are reliable and accurate. (British Pharmacopoeia 2013).

- Specificity
- Linearity
- Accuracy
- Precision
- Detection Limit
- Quantitation Limit
- Robustness
- Range

Materials and Methods

1 Materials

- Dapoxetine Hydrochloride 30 mg Tablet donates by Dr. NABIL PHARMACUTICAL COMPANY.
- Triethyl Amine (AR).
- Orthosphoric Acid (AR).
- Acetonitrile (AR).

2 Equipment

- HPLC.
- Analytical weighing balance.
- PH meter.

3 Chromatographic condition

- Column** : Inertsil ODS-3 C 18 (250×4.6mm), 5µm or equivalent.
- Flow rate**: 0.7mL/minute.
- Detector**: UV (210 nm).
- Injection volume**: 20µL.
- Run time** : 30 minute.
- Column Oven Temperature**: 30° C.

4 METHODS

4.1 Mobile phase preparation: Buffer preparation: 10 ml Triethyl Amine was Diluted In 1000 ml of distilled water. The PH was adjusted to PH 4.0 with Orthosphoric acid.

4.2 Mobile phase preparation: The buffer was made with Acetonitrile in a ratio of (600:400v/v) respectively, sonicated and filtered.

4.3 Standard control preparation: 33.6 mg of dapoxetine hydrochloride working standard were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask containing 50 ml and made up to the mark with mobile phase. 5.0 ml of this solution were diluted to 50 ml with mobile phase.

4.4 Test preparation

Accurately weighed 30mg of dapoxetine powder were transferred to a 100ml volumetric flask and completed to volume with mobile phase , 5.0 ml of this solution were diluted to 50 ml with mobile phase.

4.5 Procedure

Equal volumes (20µL) of standard and test solutions, were separately injected and record the chromatograms.

Calculation

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \text{AT} / \text{AS} \times 100$$

Where,

AT=Average area of dapoxetine Hydrochloride in with sample preparation.

AS=Average area of dapoxetine hydrochloride in standard preparation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Specificity

Specificity was demonstrated by measuring the response of the sample matrix (placebo) and mobile phase against standard Dapoxetine Hydrochloride.

Result

No significance response has been obtained that interferes with the measurement of Dapoxetine Hydrochloride.

3.2 Accuracy

Accuracy was demonstrated by adding known amounts of Dapoxetine Hydrochloride reference standard to the sample matrix and determining the measured result using the analytical procedure. Percentage recovery of measured amounts was then calculated as follows.

Table 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 show accuracy % recovery Theoretical and Actual reading at (80, 100 and 120%) at the concentrations (0.024, 0.03 and 0.036) mg/50ml.

Table 3.1 Accuracy at 80% level.

Conc. of Reference Standard	Theoretical Reading	Actual Reading	Recovery%
0.024gm/50 ml	16003.902mAu.s	16157.064 mAu.s	101.0%
0.024gm/50 ml	16003.902mAu.s	16145.352mAu.s	100.9%
0.024gm/50 ml	16003.902mAu.s	16133.028mAu.s	100.8%

Table 3.2 Accuracy at 100% level.

Conc. of Reference Standard	Theoretical Reading	Actual Reading	Recovery%
0.03 gm/50 ml	20004.877mAu.s	20039.383mAu.s	100.2%
0.03 gm/50 ml	20004.877mAu.s	19987.508mAu.s	99.90%
0.03 gm/50 ml	20004.877mAu.s	19964.256mAu.s	99.80%

Table 3.3 Accuracy at 120% level.

Conc. of Reference Standard	Theoretical Reading	Actual Reading	Recovery%
0.036gm/50 ml	24005.852mAu.s	24242.947mAu.s	101.0%
0.036gm/50 ml	24005.852mAu.s	24222.187mAu.s	100.9%
0.036gm/50 ml	24005.852mAu.s	24198.956mAu.s	100.8%

3.3 Precision

Table 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 show results of percentages of repeatability and intermediate precision.

Table 3.7 show a comparison evaluation for the results in table 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 which meet the required criteria of precision of less than 2%.

Table 3.4 Repeatability Result.

No.	Concentration	Area (mAu.s)
1	0.030gm/50ml	20039.383
2	0.030gm/50ml	19992.616
3	0.030gm/50ml	19966.954
4	0.030gm/50ml	19950.262
5	0.030gm/50ml	19961.618
6	0.030gm/50ml	19982.632
Mean		19982.244
SD		31.79515
RSD%		0.16%

3.4 Intermediate precision

Intermediate precision was conducted within laboratory variations (different analysts on different days).

Table 3.5: Analyst 1 Intermediate precision Reading.

No.	Concentration	Area (mAu.s)
1	0.030gm/50ml	20039.383
2	0.030gm/50ml	19992.616
3	0.030gm/50ml	19966.954
4	0.030gm/50ml	19950.262
5	0.030gm/50ml	19961.618
6	0.030gm/50ml	19982.632
Mean		19982.244
SD		31.79515
RSD%		0.16%

Table 3.6 Analyst 2 Intermediate precision Reading.

No.	Concentration	Area (mAu.s)
1	0.030gm/50ml	19796.502
2	0.030gm/50ml	19921.619
3	0.030gm/50ml	19882.222
4	0.030gm/50ml	19833.634
5	0.030gm/50ml	19829.028
6	0.030gm/50ml	19818.264
Mean		19846.878
SD		46.2297
RSD%		0.23

Table 3.7 Intermediate Precision Reading.

Readings	Average of Area (mAu.s)
Repeatability	19982.244
Analyst 1	19982.244
Analyst 2	19846.878
Mean	19928.32
SD	66.19638
RSD%	0.33%

3.5 Linearity

Table 3.8 and Figure 3.1 show that the correlation coefficient R^2 of 0.999 which meet the acceptance criteria.

Figure 3.1 also shows that the lowest detection and quantitation limits have the same concentration value of 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Table 3.8: Linearity Reading.

No.	Concentration	%	Area (mAu.s)
2	0.024gm / 50ml	80%	16157.064
3	0.027gm / 50ml	90%	18192.726
4	0.030gm / 50ml	100%	20039.359
5	0.033gm / 50ml	110%	22026.707
6	0.036gm / 50ml	120%	24242.947

Figure 3.1.

3.6 Detection limit

The detection limit was demonstrated by measuring the lowest concentration of Dapoxetine Hydrochloride reference standard that gives response.

The lowest concentration detected = 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

3.7 Quantitation limit

The quantitation limit was demonstrated by measuring the lowest concentration of Dapoxetine Hydrochloride reference standard that can be quantitatively determined.

The lowest concentration quantitatively determined = 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

3.8 Range

The range was derived from accuracy and linearity studies

Range is 80% - 120%.

3.9 Robustness

Robustness was demonstrated by making small deliberate changes to wavelength then analyzing samples and comparing the results to those obtained using prescribed method.

Table 3.9 shows the variation and a % Recovery of 99.2% which meet Robustness criteria of less than 1%.

Table 3.9 variation of wavelength with Area reading(mAu.s).

No.	Wavelength	mAu.s
1	211nm	19848.412
2	210nm	20004.87

- Recovery:- $\frac{19848.412 \times 100}{20004.87} = 99.2\%$
 $\frac{20004.87}{100 - 99.2} = 0.8\%$

CONCLUSION

This method is specific, precise, accurate, and linear within a given range and achieves all the requirement of Dapoxetine Hydrochloride analysis.

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